

Re-examination of Some Salient Issues on the Authorship and Recipient of Mark's Gospel

Sachia Ephraim Ikyernum ^{1*} | Silas Guda Mishi ² | Ndongesit Effeh ³

¹ Department of Religious Studies, Faculty of Arts; University of Ibadan, Ibadan, Nigeria

² Old Testament Unit, Faculty of Theology, Nigerian Christian Bible College, Akwa Ibom, Nigeria

³ New Testament Unit, Faculty of Theology, Nigerian Christian Bible College, Akwa Ibom, Nigeria

Author's Correspondence: ephraimikyernum@gmail.com

Digital Object Identifier: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10472515>

Publication History: Received 16 November 2023; Corrected and Received 8 December 2023; Accepted 24 December 2023; Available Online 9 January 2024

Abstract

Although previous scholars have discussed and come to widely accepted conclusions about the background to the gospel of Mark in terms of authorship, purpose, characteristics, structure, date, settings, and recipients of Mark's gospel, its genre as well as Sources of Mark's Gospel; which is a fact that this paper does not dispute. Yet, the essence of this paper is to re-examine some salient issues regarding the background of the gospel of Mark in terms of the author and recipient. John Mark is widely regarded as the author of the fourth gospel, but not so for the reason stated here in this paper. Although the recipient of the book is attributed to Galilee, Syria, the Decapolis and Rome; this research supports a Rome possibility because of the universality of the place and the influence of Paul on John Mark. This is the gap that we are filling here.

Keywords: Authorship, purpose, structure, date, setting, recipient, genre, source, Mark, gospel.

Introduction

The gospel of Mark according to recent scholarship is said to be the first written gospel among the four gospels. For a very long time, the gospel of Mathew was given priority as the first and earliest gospel among the synoptic. This continued until the tune of recent scholarship, which has identified Mark's gospel as the first.

A closer look at previous scholarship still affirms that apostle Peter's attendant, 'John Mark' is proposed to be the author of this gospel¹ While many came to accept this gospel as written around A.D 65-67², the motive behind its composition is said to reach the Gentiles with the good news of the kingdom and to re-interpret the nature of Jesus as the suffering messiah who has to give his life as a ransom for many. Other purposes which are said to be peculiar to Mark's gospel would seem to be to provide for the catechetical and liturgical needs of the church in Rome, to their faith in the face of the threat of martyrdom and to provide material for missionary preachers³ Although Mark the evangelist is said not to have given an orderly account of his gospel⁴ many believe that the evangelist carefully undertook a re-interpretation of the Gospel to present and defend the suffering of Jesus and the mystery of him being a messiah as servant messiah⁵ hence the verse 'Mark 10:45'.

All these above will be reviewed, although the essence of this research is to provide some valid opinions on the affirmation of Mark's gospel in terms of its authorship and recipient, which sounds differently from the others. This is the gap that we are filling here

Literature Review

This review will first begin with the purpose of Mark's gospel where C.E.B Cranfield has this to say; ...the very first verse of Mark provides a clear indication of the writer's purpose. It was to set forth 'the good news', to bear witness to Jesus as the Messiah and the Son of God. But this general purpose is common to all four gospels. The purposes which are special to Mark would seem to be to supply the catechetical and liturgical needs of the church in Rome, to support its faith in the face of the threat of martyrdom and to provide material for missionary preachers....⁶

Both R.T France⁷ Richard Baughan⁸ and Bock, D. L⁹ supports the fact Mark's gospel is modeled on the Greco-Roman biography and for a wider audience other than just Jerusalem and Rome as well as to encourage disciples in the face of persecution, appealing to the example of Jesus' suffering. Carson, D.A on the other hand opines that Mark's purpose is hard to determine, due to issues related to his sources (Redaction criticism), although he later dismisses it as having little effect on determining the purpose for the gospel of Mark. He went further to classify Mark's purpose into three categories; the first focusing on eschatology, the second on Christology, and the third on apologetics¹⁰.

On the eschatological focus, WilliMarxsen¹¹ is identified as suggesting that Mark wrote to prepare Christians for the imminent *parousia* in Galilee. Using the modern redaction criticism method, Mark focuses on Galilee,

¹ V. Taylor. The Gospel according to Mark, London: The Macmillan Press, (1966): 26

² C.E.B., Cranfield. The Gospel according to St. Mark: An Introduction and Commentary, U.K: Cambridge University Press, (1959), 8

³ C.E.B., Cranfield. The Gospel according to St. Mark: An Introduction and Commentary, U.K: Cambridge University Press, (1959), 28

⁴ E.G, Selwyn. The First Epistle of St. Peter. London, XXV, (1946): 244.

⁵ W.H, Larry., 1989. "Mark" in *New International Biblical Commentary* Peabody, MA: Hendrickson.

⁶ C.E.B., Cranfield. The Gospel according to St. Mark: An Introduction and Commentary, U.K: Cambridge University Press, (1959), 15.

⁷ R.T. France. The Gospel of Mark. NIGTC; Grand Rapids: Eerdmans, (2002).

⁸ R. J, Bauckham, ed. The Gospel for All Christians: Rethinking the Gospels Audiences. Edinburgh: T&T Clark, (1998)

⁹ D. L, Bock. "Commentaries on the Synoptic Gospels: Traditional Issues of Introduction" in Stanley, E. P. and Eckhard, J. S. ed. On the Writings of New Testament Commentaries. (2013): 8. 357

¹⁰ D.A, Carson, et al. (n.d) *An Introduction to the New Testament*. Grand Rapids, Michigan: Zondervan Publishing House 94.

¹¹ WilliMarxsen, *Mark the Evangelist*. Nashville: Abingdon, (1969).

as the place where Jesus meets with his disciples, at the expense of Jerusalem, where Jesus is rejected and killed. Jesus' command to his disciples to meet him in Galilee (Mark 14:28; cf. 16:7) was taken by Marxsen as a prediction to Mark's community of Jesus' glorious return to them. However, the meeting with Jesus to which these verses refer is clearly a post-resurrection meeting, not the *parousia*. Moreover, the geographic contrast that Marxsen (and some before him) discerns is much better explained as a reflection of the actual course of Jesus' ministry than as a theologically motivated invention of Mark's ¹².

On the Christological focus, Theodore Weeden¹³ has found in Mark a polemic against a "divine man" Christology, a way of viewing Jesus that saw him as a wonder-working hero but denied or neglected his suffering and death. To counter this tendency, Mark wrote a gospel that emphasized the humanity and suffering of Jesus. Weeden is correct to see in Mark a focus on Jesus' suffering, but he goes too far in identifying Mark's opponents as people who held to a divine-man Christology. For another, David Tiede counters that the very existence of a Hellenistic divine-man concept as a category into which early Christians would have put Jesus is open to question¹⁴.

On the apologetic aspect, S. G. F. Brandon opines that Jesus was a sympathizer with the Jewish revolutionaries, the Zealots. For this reason, he was crucified by the Romans, a method of execution generally reserved for political criminals. By branding Jesus as a rebel against Rome, his crucifixion made it very difficult for Christians to win a hearing from the Roman public particularly in the aftermath of the Jewish revolt in Palestine, when, according to Brandon, Mark wrote his gospel. To overcome this difficulty, Mark transferred as much of the blame for Jesus' death from the Romans to the Jews as he could, a process manifesting unhistorical features in the Sanhedrin and Roman trials.¹⁵ While those unhistorical features about the Sanhedrin and Roman trials that Brandon posits may be true, his appeal seems to be one of the normal apologetic that other gospel writers after him (Mathew, Luke and John) also intended to reveal.

Moreover, Gundry also supports the fact that Mark is an apologetic, written to defend the cross and Jesus suffering as part of God's plan where the cross is a cause of glory.¹⁶ Other authors tolling with this line of thought are M.D Hooker and Larry, W.H; They said that Mark seeks to re-interpret the nature of Jesus as messiah, as the suffering messiah who has to give his life as a ransom for many ¹⁷ The researcher also goes with the views of Hooker and Larry; that the evangelist carefully undertook a re-interpretation of the Gospel to present and defend the suffering of Jesus and the mystery of him being a messiah. The 'messianic secrets' is a theory first developed by William Wrede in 1901, concerning the gospel of Mark. To him, Mark wrote to depict Jesus as gathering his disciples into a secret conclave (Mark 4:11-13), where he enjoins them to secrecy about his personality. Thus, he is seen cautioning them to tell no one about him, especially after Peter's confession (Mk. 8:30). He also silences those who confesses his personality e.g. the demoniacs (Mark 1:25, 34, 3:12, 5:6, 9:20). Even in some miracles of healings, he commanded the persons not to make him known (Mark 1:43-45; 5:43; 7:36; 8:26). In some occasions, he retires from the public as though to conceal himself. The messianic secret is not concerned with the identity of the messiah, but with the nature of his task ¹⁸ as servant messiah¹⁹ hence Mark 10:45.

¹² D.A, Carson, et al. (n.d) *An Introduction to the New Testament*. Grand Rapids, Michigan: Zondervan Publishing House, 94.

¹³ T. Weeden. *Mark: Traditions in Conflict*. Philadelphia: Fortress (1971).

¹⁴ D, Tiede. *The Charismatic Figure as Miracle Worker*. Missoula, Mont: SP, (1972).

¹⁵ S.F.G, Brandon., *Jesus and the Zealots*. Manchester: Manchester University Press, (1967).

¹⁶ R. Gundry. *Mark: A Commentary on his Apology for the Cross*. Grand Rapids: Eerdmans., (1993): 1034.

¹⁷ C.E.B., Cranfield. *The Gospel according to St. Mark: An Introduction and Commentary*, U.K: Cambridge University Press, (1959):28.

¹⁸ P.M., Ralph. *Mark: Evangelist and Theologian*, South Africa: Oxford Uni. Press, (1972): 255-260.

In conclusion, the purpose of Mark is summed up with these points; first is to set forth the good news of Jesus as the Messiah and the son of God; to address the needs of the church in Rome; to support its faith in face of the threat of martyrdom, to provide materials for missionary preachers and to re-interpret Jesus' death on the cross as the act of God, and to depict him as suffering messiah. The essence of this research however is to provide some valid opinions on the affirmation of Mark's gospel in terms of its authorship and recipient, which sounds differently from the others. This is the gap that we are filling here.

Structure of Mark's Gospel

Mally, E. J.²⁰ identifies the structure of Mark's gospel, as fallen into two major sections;

1. **The Mystery of the Messiah (1:14-8:33).** This section is articulated by three summary statements (1:14-15; 3:7-12; 6:66) each of which is followed by a periscope about the disciples (1:16-20; 3:13-19; 6:7-13, 39) and ends with a notice showing how Jesus' true identity was misunderstood by the Pharisees (3:6), by his own relatives and town people (6:1-6a) even by his disciples (8:17-21, 27-30).
2. The emphasis in this section is on the miracles of Jesus; the little teaching that is recorded is mainly directed to the crowds, expressed in parables and concerned with the coming of God's reign. Jesus strives to conceal his messiah-ship (the 'messianic secret' 1:33-34; 3:12, 5:43, 7:36; 8:26), although he rebukes his disciples for their inability to understand who he is (4:13; 40, 6:52, 7:18, 8:17-21, 23).
3. **The Mystery of the Son of Man (8:27-16:8).** This part falls into three lesser sections: 8:27-10:52; 11:1-13:37; 14:1-16:8. The first of these is articulated by three predictions of the passion (8:31; 9:30-31; 10:33-34) each of which is followed by a mention of the disciple's lack of understanding (8:32-33; 9:32-34; 10:35-37) and by an instruction (8:34-38; 9:35-37; 10:35-45). The second section (11:1-13:37) is concerned with Jesus' self-revelation in Jerusalem and ends with Jesus' passing judgment on Pharisaic Judaism. The gospel concludes with the narrative of Jesus' death and resurrection (14:1-16:8). C.E.B Cranfield²¹ thus outlines Mark's gospel as follows;

- i. The Beginning, i. 1-13.
- ii. Beginnings of the Galilean Ministry, i. 14—iii. 6.
- iii. Later stages of the Galilean Ministry, iii. 7-vi. 13.
- iv. Jesus goes outside Galilee, vi. 14-viii. 26.
- v. The way to Jerusalem, viii. 27-x. 52.
- vi. Ministry in Jerusalem, xi. i-xiii. 37.
- vii. The Passion, xiv. i-xv. 47.
- viii. The Resurrection, xvi. 1-8 (9-20).

The essence of this research however is to provide some valid opinions on the affirmation of Mark's gospel in terms of its authorship and recipient, which sounds differently from the others. This is the gap that we are filling here

Date of Mark's Gospel

A lot of scholars came up with varieties of dates, regarding the composition of Mark's gospel. While some propose a date between A.D 40-60s; others predict a date in the 50s, through 70s. Below are some of them and their varying arguments;

¹⁹ W.H., Larry. "Mark" in *New International Biblical Commentary* Peabody, MA: Hendrickson. (1989). M.D, Hooker. "The Gospel according to Saint Mark" in *Black's New Testament Commentary*; Peabody, MA: Hendrickson, (1991).

²⁰ E.J, Mally., "The Gospel According to Mark" in *Jerome Biblical Commentary*. London: Geoffrey Chapman., (1970): 21.

²¹ C.E.B., Cranfield. *The Gospel according to St. Mark: An Introduction and Commentary*, U.K: Cambridge University Press, (1959).31.

A Date Between 40s-60s

One of the proponents of this date is C.C Torrey, who argues that Mark's 'abomination that causes desolation' (Mk 13:14) is a reference to the attempt in A.D 40 of the emperor Caligula to have his image set up in Jerusalem temple, and he contends that the gospel was written shortly after this²². But the identification is said to be unlikely.

Jose, O. C bases his early dating of Mark on three papyrus fragments found at Qumran (7Q5, 7Q6.1, 7Q7). Dated c.50, which he claims contains, respectively, Mark 6:52-53, 4:28, and 12:17. But most scholars have contested the identification²³. Others like Vincent Taylor suggest A.D 65-67²⁴, Glueck predicts A.D 67-69, since he feels that the gospel must have been written at the beginning of Rome's war with the Jews rather than after Jerusalem's fall²⁵. Stein on the other hand traces a lack of evidence for a post-A.D 70 perspective in Mark 13 and prefers a date of A.D 68-69²⁶

France, R.T. never explicitly discusses the date of Mark's gospel but questions the tradition that argues Mark wrote after Peter's death, while also noting Hengel's preference for a date in A.D 69²⁷. William Lane on the other hand places the gospel in the aftermath of the Neronian persecution in the second half of the sixties, agreeing with the testimony from the Anti-Macchabean prologue and Irenaeus²⁸. But in all of these predictions, scholars still dispute them, owing to one reason or the other.

A Date in the 50s, Through 70s

Hurtado Larry argues the gospel was written in a window from A.D 50-75²⁹. Cranfield³⁰ on the other hand suggests between A.D 65-70. Ben Witherington³¹, Boring³², Adela Collins³³ and Marcus, J. predict between A.D 65-75. For Ben Witherington, just like William Lane, the gospel fits a post-Neronian persecution context in which Mark is defending the need to persevere through persecution. Thus, a date in the latter period from A.D 66-70 is likely. Boring sees the gospel as written somewhere between A.D 65-75 while Marcus, J. argues that the gospel is written in the shadow of the temple's destruction, between A.D 69-74.

In the case of Adela Collins, a careful walk-through Mark 13 leads her to conclude, that the gospel is written in a window from A.D 66-74. The slight difference between what is said and what took place in A.D 70 causes her to prefer a date in A.D 68-69³⁴. However, many scholars have shown that Mark 13 has little or no evidence of being influenced by the course of events in A.D 70. That Jesus predictions reflects Old

²² C.C, Torrey. *The Four Gospels*, 2d ed. New York: Harper, (1947): 261-62.

²³ O.C, José. "Papirosneotestamentarios en la cuere 7 de Qumran," *Bib* 53, (1972): 91-100.

²⁴ V. Taylor. *The Gospel according to Mark*, London: The Macmillan Press, (1966):349.

²⁵ R.A, Guelich. *Mark 1:1-8:26. WBC 34A*: Dallas, Word, Nashville: Nelson, (1989).

²⁶ R. Stein. *Mark*. BECNT; Grand Rapids: Baker Academic, (2008): 356.

²⁷ R.T, France. *The Gospel of Mark*. NIGTC; Grand Rapids: Eerdmans, (2002):357.

²⁸ W. Lane. *The Gospel according to Mark*. NICNT: Grand Rapids: Eerdmans (1974).

²⁹ W.H., Larry. "Mark" in *New International Biblical Commentary* Peabody, MA: Hendrickson, (1989).

³⁰ C.E.B., Cranfield. *The Gospel according to St. Mark: An Introduction and Commentary*, U.K: Cambridge University Press, (1959): 15.

³¹ B. Witherington III. *The Gospel of Mark: A Socio-Rhetorical Commentary*. Grand Rapids: Eerdmans, (2001).

³² Qtd in D. A., Carson, et al. (n.d) *An Introduction to the New Testament*. Grand Rapids, Michigan: Zondervan Publishing House, 353.

³³ A.Y., Collins. *Mark*. Minneapolis: Fortress (2007)

³⁴ A.Y, Collins. *Mark*. Minneapolis: Fortress, (2007).

Testament and Jewish imagery, having to do with the besieging of cities, rather than the specific circumstances of the siege of Jerusalem³⁵.

Hooker, M.D. suggests a date around A.D. 70 somewhere between 65-75AD. This, he based on two issues; first is how the Olivet Discourse is seen (given evidence of a post-destruction setting or not?) and how early to place it in light of dating of other synoptic.³⁶ In conclusion, I go with Garland³⁷ but especially Gundry³⁸ who suggests a pre-AD 70. For the latter, it was written shortly after Peter's death. And since Papias reports that Mark the evangelist wrote this gospel from Peter's discourse and not through direct dictation, then this suggestion is likely. But for the former, he likens the gospel to have been written during the period of the war, an option Bock also regards as quite possible, while noting an earlier date in the late fifties to early sixties.

The setting of Mark's Gospel

Many scholars like Hooker, M.D Larry, Gundry, Guelieche, Ben Witherington, Stein and Adella Collins all prefer a Roman setting³⁹. While Marcus, WilliMarxsen, Vernon Barlet and Pesch suggest Syria, Galilee or Decapolis⁴⁰. However, Adella Collins suggests both Rome and Syria, while Hengel and France suggest a broader audience⁴¹. Those who prefer a Roman setting are based on these reasons;

1. The large number of Latinisms in the gospels⁴².
2. The incidental mention of Simon of Cyrene's sons, Alexander and Rufus; at least one of whom may have been known to Mark back at Rome. When writing to the Roman Church, Paul greets a particular Rufus (Rom 16:13), who may be the one earlier mentioned in Mark or not.
3. The apparently Gentile audience of the gospel
4. The many allusions to suffering, which would be appropriate if the gospel was written under the shadow of persecutions of the church in Rome.
5. The fact that 1Peter 5:13 locates Mark in Rome with Peter in the early sixties and
6. The connection with an important early centre of Christianity, which would have explained the gospel's quick acceptance.
7. And the translation of Aramaic, the explanation of terms like two lepta or the rule and the naming of the Syrophenician woman point in this direction.

Carson, D.A. *et al* in his reaction to the points above argues that numbers 1 and 3 could fit a provenance anywhere that boasted Gentiles and Latin influence. Number 6 is of questionable validity, and even if accepted, could point to several possible locations (Jerusalem, Antioch, Ephesus); numbers 4 and 5 are valid

³⁵ Bo Reicke. "Synoptic Prophecies of the Destruction of Jerusalem," in David E. Aune, ed. *Studies in New Testament and Early Christian Literature*. Supp Nov 33 Leiden: Brill, (1972):13-30.

³⁶ M.D, Hooker. "The Gospel according to Saint Mark" in *Black's New Testament Commentary*; Peabody, MA: Hendrickson, (1991).

³⁷ D. Garland. *Mark*. NIVAC; Grand Rapids: Zondervan, (1996).

³⁸ R. Gundry, *Mark: A Commentary on his Apology for the Cross*. Grand Rapids: Eerdmans, (1993).

³⁹ M.D, Hooker. "The Gospel according to Saint Mark" in *Black's New Testament Commentary*; Peabody (1991). MA: Hendrickson.; W.H., Larry, "Mark" in *New International Biblical Commentary* Peabody, MA: Hendrickson; (1989). R. Gundry, *Mark: A Commentary on his Apology for the Cross*. Grand Rapids: Eerdmans; (1993). R.A, Guelich. *Mark 1:1-8:26*. WBC 34A: Dallas, Word, Nashville: Nelson; (1989). B. Witherington III. *The Gospel of Mark: A Socio-Rhetorical Commentary*. Grand Rapids: Eerdmans, (2001). R. Stein. *Mark*. BECNT; Grand Rapids: Baker Academic (2008):35. A.Y, Collins. *Mark*. Minneapolis: Fortress (2007).

⁴⁰ WilliMarxsen, *Mark the Evangelist 1976-1980. 2 Vols.* 1:4-7; Bartlet, *St Mark*, 5-6.

⁴¹ R.T, France, *The Gospel of Mark*. NIGTC; Grand Rapids: Eerdmans, (2002): 357; M. Hengel. "Studies in the Gospel of Mark". In *Expository Times*, London: SCM. (1985).

⁴² Some of these Latinisms includes a Roman coin (Mark 12:42), a distinctively Roman/Latin name (15:16). Kümmel, 97-98.

only if Mark was written in the middle sixties, and number 3 assumes that only one Rufus exist in the early church⁴³.

Those who argue for Galilee, especially WilliMarxen, notes a positive significance accorded to Galilee in Mark. Marxen theorizes that Galilee, for Mark was the place of revelation and that the references to Jesus 'going before' the disciples into Galilee (Mk. 14:28: 16:7) were summons to Christians to gather in Galilee and await the return of Christ. However, this theory lacks conviction.

Rome seems to have a better ground for Mark's setting than other proposed locations owing to a quite number of scholars saying so. Even Morton Smith testifies that Clement of Alexandria may also have connected Mark with the Church in Alexandria. That a letter he discovered in the monastery of Mar-Saba in Egypt is an authentic letter of Clement, in which he says that Mark, after writing his gospel in Rome with Peter, came to Alexandria, where he composed a deeper, Gnostic-oriented gospel⁴⁴. Although the authenticity of the letter is disputed, at least this provides further prove on Roman setting.

The essence of this research however is to provide some valid opinions on the affirmation of Mark's gospel in terms of its authorship and recipient, which sounds differently from the others. This is the gap that we are filling here.

The Genre of Mark's Gospel

The genre of Mark's gospel is very important in this research. For Mark's gospel even though as Papias posits was not written in order, yet that does not override the fact that this gospel carries a particular genre. According to Rupert Feneberg Mark is the first person known to have taken euangellion⁴⁵ (good news) and turned it into a description of a written narrative⁴⁶. Others see the gospel as *sui generis*, meaning that *kerygma* overshadows historical report⁴⁷. Simon Legasse⁴⁸ and many others today believe the gospel is akin to some form of Greco-Roman biography.

Recent Markan commentaries surveying genre in any detail have seen this Gospel as akin to a drama, particularly a tragedy (assuming its original end to have been 16:8), a novel, a parable, an apocalypse (especially in view of chapter 13), or a liturgy of some kind⁴⁹. Mark's gospel indeed carries some of the elements of the above genres. However, the context in which this research is carried out suggests Mark is the first person known to have taken εὐαγγέλιον (good news) and turned it into a description of a written narrative, thus agreeing with the position of Rupert Feneberg.

The Sources of Mark's Gospel

The most persistent theory is that there existed a written pre-Markan passion narrative,⁵⁰ but even this idea now meets with less favor than it used to.⁵¹ Taylor, V. further reiterates that Mark did use earlier sources (Ur-

⁴³ D.A, Carson, et al. (n.d) *An Introduction to the New Testament*. Grand Rapids, Michigan: Zondervan Publishing House,

⁴⁴ M. Smith. *The Secret Gospel: The Discovery and Interpretation of the Secret Gospel According to Mark*. New York: Harper & Row (1973).

⁴⁵ εὐαγγέλιον

⁴⁶ R. Feneberg. *Der Jude Jesus und die Heide: Biographie und Theologie Jesum Markusevangelium*. Freiburg: Herder. (2000):13–17.

⁴⁷ J. Gnilka. *Das Evangelium nach Markus*. Zurich: Benziger, (19781):22–24.

⁴⁸ S.L, Legasse. *Évangile de Marc*: Paris: Cerf. (1997):29–34.

⁴⁹ J.B, Marcus. *Mark 8–16*. AB 27A; New Haven: Yale University Press, (2009):1:64–69.; L.B, Craig. "Genre in recent New Testament Commentaries". In Stanley E. Porter and Eckhard J. Schnabel. eds. *On the Writing of New Testament Commentaries*, Leiden, Boston: Lib. of Congress Cataloging-in-Pub. Data, (2013):8:73.

⁵⁰ M. Dibelius, n.d. *From Tradition to Gospel*. New York: Charles Scribner's Sons. 178-217.

⁵¹ A.R.T, John. *Redating the New Testament*. Philadelphia: Westminster, (1976): 8-16.

Markus) is suggested by the presence of doublets in his Gospel, the account of the Feeding of the Four Thousand and its sequel (8:1-26) as compared with the story of the Five Thousand and the events which followed (Mk. 6:30-7:37). The presence of 'extracts' from a sayings source (e.g. Mk. 4:21-5, 8:34, 9:1 and 9. 42-50), the peculiar character of the apocalyptic discourse in Mark 13; the signs of strata in the Passion Narrative and the absence of a parallel to 6:45-8:26 in Luke. But to determine the sources is another matter. If the conclusion on the testimony of Papias that Mark derived his message from the testimony of apostle Peter is anything to go by, then Mark's gospel's main sources come from the discourse of Peter.

The essence of this research however is to provide some valid opinions on the affirmation of Mark's gospel in terms of its authorship and recipient, which sounds differently from the others. This is the gap that we are filling here. The next section will discuss the main aim of this paper which is to suggest valid opinions and reasons regarding the authorship and recipient of Mark's gospel.

Authorship of Mark's Gospel

This is where the focus of this paper lies. The author of this gospel is widely attributed to Mark, who is in other places known as John Mark. This attribution came mostly from the early church fathers. Papias was the first to attest to this and later the likes of Iraeneus, Clement of Alexandria, Justin Martyr, Tatian, Tertullian, Origen, Jerome and Eusebius⁵² Both internal and external evidences have been proposed to this, although some are not satisfied with them. Let's begin with the external evidence.

External evidences suggest that in the words of Papias as quoted by Eusebius. *HE*, iii. 39:15, the author of Mark never added anything of his own but wrote down accurately what he received from Peter. This is what he says:

...And the Elder said this also: Mark, having become the interpreter of Peter, wrote down accurately all that he remembered of the things said and done by the Lord, but not however in order. For neither did he hear the Lord, nor did he follow Him, but afterwards, as I said, Peter, who adapted his teachings to the needs (of the hearers), but not as though he were drawing up a connected account of the Lord's oracles. So then Mark made no mistake in thus recording some things just as he remembered them, for he made it his one care to omit nothing that he had heard and to make no false statement therein....⁵³

However, some scholars dismiss these claims as secondhand evidence going back to Papias. This is the position of Kümmel⁵⁴ and Rudolf Pesch.⁵⁵ For them, Papias invented his claim about Mark's connection with Peter in order to defend the gospel against its detractors. On the contrary, Carson, D.A⁵⁶ reacts in these words;

'...Papias does not appear to be defending Mark's authorship or his connection with Peter but only the reliability of the gospel, against the charge that it lacked "order." Moreover, no dissenting voice from the early church regarding the authorship of the second gospel is found. This is surprising, since the tendency in the early church was to associate apostles with the writing of the New

⁵² D.A, Carson, et al. (n.d) *An Introduction to the New Testament*. Grand Rapids, Michigan: Zondervan Publishing House, 88.

⁵³ Qtd in V.Taylor. *The Gospel according to Mark*, London: The Macmillan Press, (1966). K. Lake, 1926. "Ecclesiastical History" in *Eusebius*. Cambridge: Harvard University Press.1.

⁵⁴ W.G, Kummel. *Introduction to the New Testament*. Nashville: Abingdon. (1975): 95.

⁵⁵ R. Pesch, "Das Markusevangelium", in *Herders Theologischer Kommentar zum Neuen Testament*. Freiburg: Herder, (1976-80):2. 1:4-7.

⁵⁶ Kgatle. *Servant Leadership in Mark 10:45 applied to African Pentecostal Christianity*. Unpublished PhD Thesis, Dept. of New Testament Studies, University of Pretoria. (2015):31.

Testament books. While we must not uncritically accept everything that early Christian writers say about the origins of the New Testament, we should not reject what they say without good reason. The early and uncontested claim that Mark wrote the second gospel based on Peter's teaching can be overturned only by rather clear indications to the contrary from the gospel itself ...⁵⁷.

While the researcher agrees with Carson to some extent, one should not also forget that there are certain traditions among the early church that Mark employed in the course of his writing⁵⁸. Even his style of writing and vocabulary (Mark 7:32, 8:3) suggest some modifications in the course of collecting some of his information from Peter's discourse. As such, Papias claim of Peter's accurate dictation of some sort may not be entirely true.

In another argument, most of the scholars oppose the Papias tradition given the fact that nowhere in the gospel does the author reveals his identity. That somewhere in the beginning of the second century, Christians started writing on the manuscript 'according to the gospel of Mark' that Mark was a very common Roman name and so that means, the author could be any other Roman person, not necessarily Mark the apostle. And by the middle of the century, a Christian leader 'Papias' attributed the gospel to Mark, the interpreter of Peter⁵⁹ but Sanner responds that although Mark was a Roman name, there is no reason to think that he was not a Jew by birth, because Saul too being a Jew, also had a Roman name⁶⁰

Other later apostolic church fathers also did an explicit analysis of some portion of Papias claim of John Mark, Peter's attendant as the author of Mark's gospel, this is what they say. For Iraeneus (Circa 130 C.E), Mark was Peter's attendant and disciple who wrote down this gospel in Rome, following the death of Paul and Peter. In the words of Clement of Alexandria (Circa 215 C.E), Peter was even aware of Mark's writing of this gospel and for Origen (Circa 250 C.E), Peter asked Mark his attendant to put down in writing this gospel⁶¹.

On internal evidence, scholars like English, D⁶² Henry, M⁶³Geisler, N.L⁶⁴ and C.H Dodd⁶⁵ among others first gave a sketch of the bibliography of the author of Mark's gospel

- I. That the account is vivid and detailed, revealing contact with Jesus inner circle (Peter, James and John)
- II. He used Peter's words and deeds (Mark 8:29)
- III. He alone added 'and Peter in the resurrection account (Mark 16:8)
- IV. There is striking similarity between his broad outline and Peter's sermon in Acts 10:34-43
- V. He was familiar with the geography of the land and Jerusalem. (Mark 5:1, 6:53, 8:10, 11:1,13:3)
- VI. He knew Aramaic, the common language of the day (Mark 5:41, 7:11, 34, 14:36)
- VII. He understood Jewish institutions and cultures. (Mark 1:21, 2:14, 16, 18, 7:2-4)

⁵⁷ D.A, Carson, et al. *An Introduction to the New Testament*. Grand Rapids, Michigan: Zondervan Publishing House, (n.d): 88.

⁵⁸ M.S, Kgatle. *Servant Leadership in Mark 10:45 applied to African Pentecostal Christianity*. Unpublished PhD Thesis, Dept. of New Testament Studies, University of Pretoria, (2015): 32

⁵⁹ M.A, Powell. *Introducing the New Testament: A Historical, Literary and Theological Survey*. Grand Rapids: Baker Academic, (2009): 128.

⁶⁰A.E, Sanner., *The Gospel according to Mark*. Kansas City: Beacon Hill. (1979): 244.

⁶¹ Qtd in E. Van Eck. *Introduction to the New Testament: The Synoptic Problem and Introduction to and Exegesis and Theology of Mark*. University of Pretoria. Faculty of Theology. Dept of New Testament Studies, Pretoria, (2013):19.

⁶² D. English. "The Message of Mark". In Stott. ed. J.R.W. Leichester: Inter-varsity Press, (1992).

⁶³ M. Henry, "The New Mathew Henry Commentary". In Manser, M.H ed. Grand Rapids: Zondervan, (2010): 1566.

⁶⁴ N.L, Geisler, *A Popular Survey of the New Testament*. Grand Rapids: Baker books, (2007):68.

⁶⁵ C.H, Dodd. "The Framework of the Gospel Narrative," in *Expository Times* (1932):43: 396-400.

The Recipient of Mark's Gospel

Based on the identification of Mark's settings, there are two possibilities regarding where the gospel of mark was written for. First is the possibility of Rome and second is the possibility of Galilee, Syria and the Decapolis. In this respect, France, R.T⁶⁶ argues that since Mark's gospel was intended to circulate widely, means that determining the setting is not so important. For this emphasis, he appeals to a work by Richard Bauckham⁶⁷ who argues the gospels were composed for a broad audience. D.A Carson, on the contrary argues for Rome, given this statement below;

..The extra-biblical sources points to a Gentile Christian audience, probably in Rome. The Roman destination of Mark's gospel is simply an inference from its Roman provenance. If Mark wrote in Rome, he probably wrote to Romans. This is either stated or implied in the early traditions about the gospel, which have Mark recording the preaching of Peter for those who had heard the great apostle in Rome.... the many Latinisms of the gospel are compatible with, if not conclusive for, a Roman audience. That Mark writes to Gentiles seems clear from his translation of Aramaic expressions, his explanation of Jewish customs (such as the washing of hands before eating [7:3-4]), and, in the few texts he includes on the subject, his interest in the cessation of the ritual elements in the Mosaic law (see Mark 7:1-23, esp. v. 19; 12:32-34)⁶⁸.

Going by issues raised above, it could be that Mark's gospel was intended for Rome, while Galilee is out of the equation, given the evidence raised concerning the setting of Mark's gospel. And at the same time, the gospel was intended for a broader audience as Bauckham and France, suggested. This fact is evident, since Rome by this time became the centre of world civilization. As such, every tribe of the nation was widely represented in this city. Besides; John Mark would have considered the need to take the gospel of Christ to this place foreseeing that the great commission statement was for the word of God to reach the whole earth.

Besides, the author seemed to have been influenced by the ministry of Paul, having worked together in their first missionary journey, before he returned to Jerusalem. Paul is seen as being keen to reach Rome with the gospel even when he had a chance to be freed by Festus and Agrippa (Acts 25:1-22). His resolve for Rome was so strong that his end was also there. Such an experience would have shaped his thoughts and drive as he wrote down the gospel, having witnessed the demand of Paul while on trial in Jerusalem. John Mark must have also noticed that since Rome was the centre of the world, where every tribe, tongue, race, colour and sex meet, then sending such a message to them would seem desirable to him rather than limiting its scope only to places like Syria, Galilee and Decapolis. He must have also noticed that the dreaded persecution in Jerusalem and the surrounding cities where Christians were staying would soon wipe the Christian faith if efforts were not made to preserve in writing the gospel message and sending it to the heathen as far as Rome. Thus, agreeing with Rome and at the same time beyond Roman recipient for the gospel of Mark is not out of place.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the resolution to the summary of the arguments and counter-arguments of the various backgrounds to Mark's gospel is that;

- I. John Mark is the author of Mark's gospel
- II. His purpose is to set forth the good news of Jesus as the Messiah and son of God. To address the needs of the church in Rome. To support its faith in the midst of martyrdom. To provide materials for missionary preachers. And finally, to re-interpret Jesus' death on the cross as the act of God as well as depict him as 'suffering Messiah'

⁶⁶ R.T, France. *The Gospel of Mark*. NIGTC; Grand Rapids: Eerdmans, 357; M. Hengel. 1985. "Studies in the Gospel of Mark". *In Expository Times*, London: SCM (2002).

⁶⁷ R.J, Bauckham, ed. *The Gospel for All Christians: Rethinking the Gospels Audiences*. Edinburgh: T&T Clark, (1998).

⁶⁸ D.A, Carson, et al. *An Introduction to the New Testament*. Grand Rapids, Michigan: Zondervan Publishing House, (n.d): 94.

- III. Mark's gospel has a clear indication of a gentile purpose, thereby justifying the context (Nigeria) in which this research is focused. The gospel is written in a raw fashion, and that also coincides with the way and manner Mark wrote about the incidence of the request, from the two sons of Zebedee, as depicted earlier in Mark 10:45. The 'Son of Man' title as seen in Mark and other synoptic demonstrates clearly, as to how Jesus used the title to refer to his humanistic nature, despite other lingering opinions about the title by others. Thus, Mark was written with the common language of every day Greek.
- IV. Mark's structure is centered on two major parts; 'the mystery of the messiah' (1:14-8:33) and the 'mystery of the son of man' (8:27-16:8).
- V. The date in which Mark's gospel was written is around pre-AD 70. It was written shortly after Peter's death. And since Papias reports that Mark the evangelist wrote this gospel from Peter's discourse and not through direct dictation, then this suggestion is likely.
- VI. Rome seems to have a strong background for the settings of Mark's gospel.
- VII. The gospel was intended for Rome but at the same time, for a broader audience. This fact is evident, since Rome by this time became the centre of world civilization. As such, every tribe of the nation was widely represented in this city. Also, the influence of Paul on John Mark for the gospel to reach Rome is not out of point.
- VIII. Mark is the first person known to have taken *εὐαγγέλιον* (good news) and turned it into a description of a written narrative.
- IX. Finally, Mark derived his message from the testimony of the discourse of Peter.

Bibliography

- Bartlet, V., *St Mark*. London: Thomas Nelson & Son, (n.d).
- Bauckham, R.J. ed. *The Gospel for All Christians: Rethinking the Gospels Audiences*. Edinburgh: T&T Clark (1998).
- Bo Reicke. "Synoptic Prophecies of the Destruction of Jerusalem," in David E. Aune, ed. *Studies in New Testament and Early Christian Literature*. Supp Nov 33 Leiden: Brill. (1972):121-33
- Bock, D.L., "Commentaries on the Synoptic Gospels: Traditional Issues of Introduction" in Stanley, E. P. and Eckhard, J. S. ed. *On the Writings of New Testament Commentaries* Leiden Boston: Library of Congress Cataloging-in-Publication (2013): 8. 357.
- Brandon, S.F.G. *Jesus and the Zealots*. Manchester: Manchester University Press (1967).
- Carson, D.A et al. *An Introduction to the New Testament*. Grand Rapids, Michigan: Zondervan Publishing House (n.d).
- Collins, A.Y. *Mark*. Minneapolis: Fortress (2007).
- Cranfield, C.E.B. *The Gospel according to St. Mark: An Introduction and Commentary*, U.K: Cambridge University Press. (1959).
- Dibelius, M. *From Tradition to Gospel*. New York: Charles Scribner's Sons (n.d).
- Dodd, C. H. "The Framework of the Gospel Narrative," in *Expository Times* 43. (1932) 396-400
- Douglas, J.D & Tenney, M.C. *Zondervan Illustrated Bible Dictionary*. Grand Rapids: Zondervan, (2011).
- Eck, V., 2013. "Mission, Identity and Ethics in Mark: Jesus the Patron for Outsiders". In *HTS*

Teologiese Studies/Theological Studies.69 (1).Retrieved on 1st/09/2018 from <https://dx.doi.org/10.4102/hts.v69i1>.

- English, D. "The Message of Mark". In Stott. ed. J.R.W. Leichester: Inter-varsity Press, (1992).
- Feneberg, R. *Der Jude Jesus und die Heide: Biographie und Theologie Jesuim Markusevangelium*. Freiburg: Herder, (2000).
- France, R.T. *The Gospel of Mark*. NIGTC; Grand Rapids: Eerdmans, (2002).
- Garland, D. *Mark*. NIVAC; Grand Rapids: Zondervan, (1996).
- Geisler, N.L. *A Popular Survey of the New Testament*. Grand Rapids: Baker books, (2007).
- Gnilka, J. *Das Evangelium nach Markus*. Zurich: Benziger, (1978):1:22–24.
- Guelich, R.A. Mark 1:1-8:26. WBC 34A: Dallas, Word, Nashville: Nelson, (1989).
- Gundry, R. *Mark: A Commentary on his Apology for the Cross*. Grand Rapids: Eerdmans, (1993).
- Hawkins, J.C. *Horae Synopticae, 2nd ed*. Oxford: Oxford University Press. (1909)
- Hengel, M. "Studies in the Gospel of Mark". In *Expository Times*, London: SCM, (1985).
- Henry, M. "The New Mathew Henry Commentary". In Manser, M.H ed. Grand Rapids: Zondrvan, (2010).
- Hooker, M.D. "The Gospel according to Saint Mark" in *Black's New Testament Commentary*; Peabody, MA: Hendrickson, (1991).
- John, A. T. R. *Redating the New Testament*. Philadelphia: Westminster, (1976).
- John, R. D., 1976. "Introduction: From Passion Traditions to Passion Narrative," in Werner H. Kelbered. *The Passion in Mark: Studies on Mark 14-16*, Philadelphia: Fortress.
- José, O.C. "Papiros neotestamentarios en la cuere 7 de Qumran," *Bib* (1976):53, 91-100.
- Kgatle, M.S. *Servant Leadership in Mark 10:45 applied to African Pentecostal Christianity*. Unpublished PhD Thesis, Dept. of New Testament Studies, University of Pretoria, (2015).
- Kummel, W.G. *Introduction to the New Testament*. Nashville: Abingdon, (1975).
- Lake, K.. "Ecclesiastical History" in *Eusebius*. Cambridge: Harvard University Press, (1926).
- Lane, W. *The Gospel according to Mark*. NICNT: grand Rapids: Eerdmans (1974).
- Larry, W. H. "Mark" in *New International Biblical Commentary* Peabody, MA: Hendrickson, (1989).
- Hooker, M.D. "The Gospel according to Saint Mark" in *Black's New Testament Commentary*; Peabody, MA: Hendrickson, (1991).
- Legasse, S., L. *Évangile de Marc*. Paris: Cerf. (1997).

- Mally, E. J. "The Gospel According to Mark" in *Jerome Biblical Commentary*. London: Geoffrey Chapman, (1970).
- Marcus, J. B. *Mark 8–16*. AB 27A; New Haven: Yale University Press, (2009).
- Craig, L. B. "Genre in recent New Testament Commentaries". In Stanley E. Porter and Eckhard J. Schnabel. eds. *On the Writing of New Testament Commentaries*, Leiden, Boston: Lib. of Congress Cataloging-in-Pub. Data, (2013):8:73.
- Pesch, R. "Das Markusevangelium", in *Herders Theologischer Kommentar zum Neuen Testament*. Freiburg: Herder, (197680):2(1):4-7.
- Powell, M.A. *Introducing the New Testament: A Historical, Literary and Theological Survey*. Grand Rapids: Baker Academic, (2009).
- Ralph, P.M. *Mark: Evangelist and Theologian*, South Africa: Oxford Uni. Press, (1972).
- Sanner, A.E. *The Gospel according to Mark*. Kansas City: Beacon Hill, (1979).
- Selwyn, E. G. *The First Epistle of St. Peter*. London, (1946): XXV
- Smith, M. *The Secret Gospel: The Discovery and Interpretation of the Secret Gospel According to Mark*. New York: Harper & Row, (1973).
- Stein, R. *Mark*. BECNT; Grand Rapids: baker Academic, (2008).
- Streeter, B.H. *Four Gospels: A Study of Origins*, London, (1924).
- Swete, H. B. *The Gospel according to St. Mark*. 3rd ed. London, (1920).
- Taylor, V. *The Gospel according to Mark*, London: The Macmillan Press, (1966).
- Tiede, D. *The Charismatic Figure as Miracle Worker*. Missoula, Mont: SP, (1972).
- Torrey, C.C. *The Four Gospels*, 2d ed. New York: Harper, (1947).
- Van Eck, E. *Introduction to the New Testament: The Synoptic Problem and Introduction to and Exegesis and Theology of Mark*. University of Pretoria. Faculty of Theology. Dept of New Testament Studies, Pretoria. (2013).
- Weeden, T. *Mark: Traditions in Conflict*. Philadelphia: Fortress, (1971).
- Willi Marxsen. *Mark the Evangelist*. Nashville: Abingdon, (1969).
- Willian, Wrede. *The Messianic Secret*. Great Britain: Lutterworth Press, (1971).
- Witherington. III, B. *The Gospel of Mark: A Socio-Rhetorical Commentary*. Grand Rapids: Eerdmans, (2001).